

Evidence of what exactly? Questioning the use of neural networks to create evidence within research narratives

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Whenever we present research, there is the desire to tell a believable narrative. Whether it is the way that the experiment was conducted or our hypothesis for what the results indicate, both oral and written papers ultimately aim to persuade. However, when building an argument within academia, rhetoric alone is not sufficient; the presentation of evidence is a pivotal element of any paper. Yet, the standards for what constitutes evidence differ between the humanities and sciences – posing a challenge to researchers who attempt to straddle both. This paper explores the extent to which the outputs of neural networks – such as the results of computer vision pipelines or topic modelling – conform to either of these standards. There are numerous precedents for the utilisation of such models.

The use of machines, such as cameras, for generating evidence is well established. Extending beyond human perception – capturing particles not seen by the naked eye or galaxies thousands of light-years away – their outputs are used to expand our scientific understanding of the world. Yet cameras are also capable of producing distortions, ranging from field curvature and lens flare to their inherent inability to document what lies outside the frame. However, through a clear understanding of these limitations and subjectivities, it is often possible to extrapolate either the attributes of the object or scene represented. While interpretation is inherent to the process of creating photographs, explainability and transparency are pivotal in their use as evidence.

Yet, for machine learning applications, the distinction between distortion and the object of study remains unclear. There is a variability to the distortions or biases introduced within a model: they are not the same for all data and cannot be predicted beforehand. Moreover, they are not only structural, as in the case of photography (at least before any AI-driven post-processing), but emerge as a combination of the training data and the model architecture, serving as lenses. Consequently, it is difficult to separate patterns learned from the data from those introduced by the model. In short, the model can inadvertently obscure the very cultural and historical trends that we are trying to identify (Bode, 2020; Impett and Offert, 2022).

In this paper, we aim to disentangle the dataset lens from the model architecture lens. We gather three multimodal datasets of the Japanese prints and paintings collections from the Tokyo National Museum, the Victoria and Albert Museum, and the Rijksmuseum. These datasets – similar, but shaped by different implicit cultural frameworks – are used to highlight the ways in which inherent cultural biases are exaggerated and warped by different model architectures. We use these datasets to highlight the methodological assumptions and technical limitations of three approaches to three latent-space models: StyleGAN, masked autoencoders, and CLIP. In each collection ‘anchor’ artworks – those that appear, slightly modified, across all datasets – were identified through computing a perceptual hash (pHash) and used to create relative latent spaces (Moschella et al., 2023). The relative spaces are then used to explore the impact of different architectures on the resulting embedding spaces and highlight how sensitive the outputs are to different forms of bias.

Furthermore, we show that the evaluation and visualisation processes only compound these issues. An enormous amount of variation can be achieved by varying model architecture parameters, altering training parameters, and performing dimensionality reduction. In many

applications, this variability is not a problem. When there is a discreet task, a test dataset can be used to evaluate the performance of models trained with different parameters. However, for most digital humanities applications, categories within results – such as clusters and topics – are not predefined, and a more exploratory approach is taken. This makes choosing among different models difficult, as there is no labelled test dataset to evaluate performance. While metrics, such as topic coherence and silhouette scores, can be used to evaluate the resulting clustering, they measure the quality of the clusters – whether they overlap or are densely populated – not how well they reflect reality (Suraya, Sholeh and Lestari, 2023; Murugaraj *et al.*, 2025). It is therefore easy to inadvertently optimise a model to produce ‘good’ clusters, that are a poor reflection of the relationships within the data. When working with humanities data in particular, edge cases or anomalies are often of particular importance, highlighting signs of connections and change worth further exploration. Therefore, the digital humanities’ position between the sciences and humanities, renders many existing evaluative frameworks for evidence irrelevant for evaluation.

Yet, the alternative is to leave evaluation to human discretion. While the humanities and social sciences present several methods for acknowledging the researcher’s subjective interpretation, this approach likely to result in models that are inadvertently optimised so that the output aligns to preconceived notions of what the data *should* look like. The many other outputs generated using different parameters, which may support alternative – even contradictory – interpretations, are effectively discarded. This means that researchers are more likely to reinforce the established narrative about a topic, as the outputs that replicate this model are deemed to be better or more ‘comprehensible’.

Under these circumstances, what frameworks would it be necessary to adopt for researchers to accept the outputs of AI models in the same manner as photographs (Ralske, 2025)? Can we really treat these outputs as evidence? We will use our multimodal dataset as a foundation to explore what can or cannot be projected in the model’s internal representation of the data (latent space), highlighting what is amplified, and what is underrepresented. We unpick the internal representations of different models to highlight how the relationships between data change depending on choices made during training and visualisation and how this consequently shapes our understanding of the data.

Cited Works

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